

Factors Influencing Initial Coin Offering (ICO) Growth in Asian Countries: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

Initial Coin Offering (ICO) is a breakthrough in fundraising actions carried out by company owners. It is an innovative type of venture funding through cryptocurrency and blockchain technology, and it is a breakthrough in fundraising actions carried out by start-ups. This fundraising activity exists in a single country, but it has extended to every country in the world. According to the website icobench.com, there were 1289 initial coin offerings (ICOs) in Asia between 2013 and 2021. Many aspects of initial coin offerings (ICOs) remain unknown, giving a great deal of potential for further investigation, including the factors that influence the success of ICO initiatives. We looked at the success of initial coin offering (ICO) projects with the primary goal of identifying the elements that influence project outcomes, particularly in Asian countries, as part of our research. In this way, the objective and uniqueness of this study serve as the foundation for future research into the critical elements impacting the growth of initial coin offerings (ICOs). Systematic Literature Review was the research methodology that was used (SLR). Previous research articles were gathered from 12 top publishers and 63 research-related publications relevant to the growth and success of initial coin offerings (ICOs). In the end, we discovered six characteristics that influenced the rise of ICOs.

Keywords: *Initial Coin Offering, ICO, Blockchain, Crowdfunding, Token.*

INTRODUCTION

Technological start-ups are currently gaining the attention of many investors and have raised significant sums of money, which has piqued the curiosity of researchers in the field of corporate finance (Ozili, 2018; Gomber et al., 2017; Chang et al., 2020). To be successful, new ventures require resources. One of the most critical resources is the ability to obtain financing (Sapienza, 1992; Bernardino & Santos, 2020; Gompers et al., 2020). Fundraising for entrepreneurial enterprises is made more difficult by agency problems, knowledge asymmetry, a lack of flows, and the absence of assurances (Ang, 1991; Chod & Lyandres, 2021). There are numerous obstacles that entrepreneurs must overcome when using traditional investment mechanisms, which raise the price of doing business and increases the risk of credit banking institutions. Technology firms have successfully attracted a large number of investors and raised substantial sums of money (Myalo & Glukhov, 2016; Moxoto et al., 2021). It has become a matter of discussion in entrepreneurial finance that fundraising to finance initiatives for start-ups has taken on various forms and techniques in recent years (Courtney et al., 2017; Catalini & Gans, 2018; Fisch, 2019). ICO stands for Initial Coin Offering. It is a new approach or mechanism to acquire funds for a start-up company in its early stages by leveraging contributions from many blockchain-based individuals (Courtney et al., 2017; Howell et al., 2020).

Initial coin offering (ICO) projects promote creative financing concepts worldwide, thereby democratizing financial investment and enabling a new degree of reach previously impossible through conventional means (Campino et al., 2022). High-tech solutions and the role of e-commerce have become critical, particularly as significant contributions to keeping the economy going during times of crisis (Weinstein, 2012). The initial coin offering project is a blockchain-based technological enterprise financed with cryptocurrency (Martino et al., 2020). Investing in cryptocurrencies necessitates converting fiat currency to the digital currency (Ahamad et al., 2013). Tokens must be given to investors when their money has been transferred to the project's promoter. Initial coin offers (ICO) allow for a wide range of token types (Adhami et al. 2018): (i) monetary tokens, such as cryptocurrencies, for exchange and storage; (ii) security tokens, which function similarly to traditional securities but utilize a blockchain infrastructure; and (iii) utility tokens, which bestow the investor with the right to access a product or service.

Alternative investments like ICOs, according to Block et al. (2021), allow for direct funding from global investors and help democratize entrepreneurship and capital markets. As a low-risk means of obtaining funding, initial coin offerings (ICOs) have been compared to other types of financing such as initial public offerings (IPOs), venture capital funds (VCs), and fundraising (Fisch, 2019). 2019 (Kranz et al.). However, different models exhibit distinct traits and are worth studying independently. Academics have continued to pay attention to initial coin offerings, and various research has been conducted on them (Roosenboom et al., 2018). It was identical, as it was the determining factor in their success.

Nonetheless, there is still more literature to be reviewed on this subject (Ahmad et al., 2021), specifically project success factors in general and the role of variable capital in particular (Fisch, 2019).

An ICO project's success may be influenced by the quantity of money it raises. There's a tall-up. The amount of money that can be raised in an ICO depends on various factors, including but not limited to: There are three types of funding caps: unlimited, soft-cap, and hard-cap. Unlimited funding means no constraints on how much money can be raised for a project. For example, (iv) collect and return; (v) dynamic ceiling; (vi) a hard cap is calculated, and if it's exceeded, tokens are distributed based on the ratio of the total cash received to the hard cap. This quality is combined with others in various ways (vi). Initial coin offering (ICO) is a "decentralized financing strategy, where the company needs" capital by issuing coins to online investors, which can be classified as an ICO. Tokens (sometimes known as "coins") are digital tokens based on the blockchain that may be traded among investors (Huang et al., 2020). One of the essential aspects of ICO ventures is the existence of a secondary market for their tokens. Purchase and resell tokens.

There have been 5,470 campaigns completed as of November 2019, according to the ICOBench website, with 1,785 of them succeeding and 3,685 of them falling short. The greatest money has been raised from digital token sales in the following industries: The platform includes various other business services, including infrastructure, finance, and more. In terms of the number of token campaigns launched in 2018 and 2019, the United States, Singapore, and Hong Kong are among the top three countries. The Baltic states of Estonia and Lithuania, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom had the most completed offers in Europe during that time period.

It is emerging as a promising study focus in the larger field of entrepreneurial research in this setting (Cohen & Wirtz, 2021; Bonini & Capizzi, 2019). There has been a surge in the number of studies on ICOs from 2017 to 2019 of 700 percent. In 2017, Google Bachelor produced 280 articles about the subject. There were 848 articles on the subject published in the two years of 2017-2018. More than 2000 articles were published between 2017 and the end of 2019. A research field's intrinsic interdisciplinary nature is demonstrated by the use of integration theory and concepts from disciplines such as the law, example Kaal (2018) and in the areas of computing and engineering.

Research on ICOs is difficult to arrange and systematize since they are constantly expanding in scope and have a wide range of different characteristics. The following is the sequence of events: In the following section, we define the word "ICO." After that, we'll go over the research strategy and literature that we employed. In the following sections, we explain how to measure development in various ways, and we conclude the book with a methodical approach. An investigation into how investment in initial coin offerings (ICOs) has evolved throughout Asian countries, with a focus on those where ICOs have taken off, such as Singapore and Hong Kong, is presented in this study. We compile the findings into a single thematic report and make recommendations for other areas of study. Let us wrap up by summarizing what we've discussed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Initial Coin Offering (ICO)

ICO is a new fundraising mechanism and method based on cryptographically secured blockchain, generally referred to as tokens that are then issued and sold to investors to finance projects (Chen, 2018; Arnold et al., 2019). Furthermore, the ICO is carried out by offering stock tokens with the promise that the tokens will be operated as a medium of exchange when carrying out digital platform services that token issuers have developed (Belitski & Boreiko, 2021; Momtaz, 2021). Fisch's (2019) research explains that ICOs use Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), i.e., blockchain with token sales, to increase capital. Raising funds through ICOs allows entrepreneurs to raise large amounts of funds with little effort and in a short time. He further explained that the failure of the ICO project could make it difficult and detrimental to project members and investors (Xu et al., 2021). Further, Spinedi et al. (2019) stated that ICOs are not just a new approach to financing but make it possible for the parties involved, i.e., entrepreneurs, companies and investors, to build various direct relationships, thus generating different types of token-based communities, depending on the specific objectives of the ICO. Apart from that, ICO is also defined as raising funds through open calls promoted by companies, organizations, and entrepreneurs in exchange for tokens which can then be sold or used for profit in the future.

This sector is currently unregulated because of a lack of many rules. As a result, the importance of high-quality cues is much greater (Bourveau et al., 2018). The lack of regulation in ICO ventures distinguishes them from other ventures. Initial public offerings (IPO) and venture capital (VC) have been used to compare IPO, but these concepts have substantial differences (Biasi & Chakravorti, 2019). The use of a public Internet platform to solicit contributions of any kind (money, goods, services, or volunteer time). The crowd can receive tangible or intangible benefits from crowdsourcing. Fundraising takes place most often on online platforms that link fundraisers and funders—the authors (Boreiko and Risteski, 2021). However, most ICOs do not give equity rights, unlike reward crowdfunding, allowing investors to enjoy the final product once it is launched. As a result, both sources of funding offer early project support. An ICO is a form of crowdfunding that uses a blockchain to raise money. The difference between crowdfunding and ICOs can be summarized: crowdfunding does

not employ a centralized platform to conduct due diligence on a project, but ICOs do. As opposed to ICOs, companies using crowdfunding may have to decide the pricing of goods before (OECD, 2019). For ICOs, a secondary market and liquidity are the most important distinguishing factors (Brochado, 2018).

ICO Success

Success in an initial coin offering (ICO) is possible when businesses, organizations, or entrepreneurs accomplish and finish project objectives (Zhao et al., 2021). Investors benefit significantly when an ICO is booming or when marketable tokens are used. Additionally, Liu & Wang (20119) stated that an ICO is successful when it meets its fundraising goal, successfully registers tokens in the crypto market, or generates good profits following the ICO. Additionally, success factors can be classified into the following categories based on their scope: (i) success factors for the project; (ii) success elements for the campaign; (iii) success factors for social media; and (iv) success factors for human capital.

The success factors for the project are the project's features. Namely, each attribute stated before the ICO started and related to the proposed idea and its anticipated conclusion. All scholars in this field do not universally define the success of a project. To account for the possibility of receiving inconsistent results, some studies conducted their analyses using alternative success metrics yet obtained comparable results (De Jong et al., 2018). This market is crucial to an ICO project since it is seen as an indicator of how successful a project has been. If the token is sold on the secondary market, then the project is considered to have been successful (Amsden & Schweizer, 2019).

The success of the campaign is judged by how well the relevant components of the campaign have been planned and executed prior to and throughout the campaign period. Popular belief is that a longer campaign has a negative impact on the project's performance, whereas shorter campaigns nearly always yield greater results (Kolk & Jong, 2020). Pre-sale of tokens is common practice, with early investors obtaining discounts and benefits for doing so (Liu & Wang, 2019). However, there are concerns about the negative repercussions of presales, as presales may be perceived as an immediate demand for funds and result in the dumped tokens in the secondary market (Palazzo & Rabetti, 2019; Roosenboom et al., 2020). Since bigger bonuses are seen as probable scams, their existence may have a negative impact on an ICO's viability and success (Amsden & Schweizer, 2019).

In today's world, efficient use of social media platforms can assist promote a project and influence investors' behavior, which in turn can have an impact on the project's success (Liu & Wang, 2019). The most popular social media channels for ICO campaigns are Twitter and Github, the latter of which is a public code repository. Because high-intensity engagement on Twitter is linked to favorable returns in the near term but negative returns in the long term, it is important that Twitter usage be constant and not overblown, even when it positively corresponds with market capitalization. Twitter accounts may be used to better communicate with investors and reduce information asymmetries similar to what happens in crowdfunding, therefore demonstrating the value of having a Twitter account for ICO projects (Greenberg et al., 2013). Token presales are boosted by the project's use of the Github platform as a repository for publicly accessible code (Roosenboom et al., 2020).

In the past, several studies have focused on the importance of human capital to business performance. According to Giudici and Adhami (2019), these are the major characteristics of the founding team: The following factors are taken into consideration: (a) professional expertise; (b), involvement in blockchain projects; (c) entrepreneurial profile; and (d) founder count and social media presence. A project's success is closely linked to the size of the founding team and the number of advisors, as larger teams provide better results. Communication and bridging of knowledge gaps are crucial in new enterprises, and the size of the team plays a significant role in this (Jin et al., 2017).

The Systematic Literature Review

An SLR, or systematic literature review in Indonesian, is a way of doing a literature review that identifies, analyses, and interprets all findings on a study issue in order to answer research questions that were previously established (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007). Systematic Literature Review (SLR) avoids prejudice and subjective understanding of researchers by carefully following steps and protocols (Garcia Holgado et al., 2020). Secondary research is the subject of a systematic review (secondary study). In order to provide policymakers with information that is more complete and balanced, a systematic review is a helpful tool. It is a research method that summarizes preliminary findings in order to give more complete and balanced facts. Meta-analysis, on the other hand, can be used to statistically synthesize results (quantitative techniques).

There are a few things to keep in mind when it comes to SLR. By incorporating the research team in summarizing research findings, a scientific methodological approach can be used. SLR often employs a research protocol in which the search for research results and articles is carried out systematically. There are specific criteria for which articles will be included, and the methodology is followed to the letter. Reduces the likelihood of prejudice. It is possible to reproduce, and Results might be synthesized by meta-analysis or through storytelling (meta-synthesis) (Kitchenham, 2004). The SLR method will make finding essential factors in discussing ICO success easier. This method will be the basis for the development of further research and discussion of related factors.

METHOD

As with individual research approaches, systematic review research begins with the development of a protocol for systematic review research and concludes with the conduct of systematic review research. Similarly to how quantitative and qualitative approaches are used in general research, a systematic review employs both quantitative and qualitative methods. A quantitative systematic review method employs a quantitative methodology to summarize research findings (Meta-analysis). Meta-analysis is defined as a strategy for pooling data in order to increase statistical power (Statistical power) in establishing a causal association between a risk factor or therapy and an effect (Outcome) (Perry & Hammond, 2002). Meanwhile, a qualitative technique is used to synthesize (summarize) the outcomes of descriptive qualitative research in a systematic review. Meta-synthesis is the process of synthesizing (summarizing) the outcomes of qualitative research. Meta-synthesis, by definition, is the process of integrating data in order to develop new ideas or conceptions or a more complete understanding (Perry & Hammond, 2002). In the search process, three keywords were used, namely, "Initial Coin Offering," "Success," and "Fundraising." Papers selected and used in the last five years aim to find the topic's relevance to previous research publications. The search was conducted using papers from 12 leading publishers such as IEEE, Elsevier, Sage, Emerald, Taylor and Francis, Springer, and Scopus. In the end, several important factors were obtained regarding the factors that could affect the growth of the ICO.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Initial Coin Offering (ICO) Market

The sale of crypto tokens ("tokens") in an ICO serves as a means of raising capital for blockchain-related enterprises (Boreiko & Risteski, 2021; Chod & Lyandres, 2021). As a general rule, utility tokens grant holders access to a service or product that the issuer will provide, while security tokens grant holders financial rights such as voting and dividends (Rohr & Wright 2017), as well as tangible assets such as art and real estate (Momtaz 2021), debt-like rights, and tangible assets like art and real estate (Barsan, 2017). However, whereas ICOs have usually been associated with the issuance of utility tokens, the blockchain industry has traditionally used the term "STOs" to refer to the issue of tokens with security features.

On a cryptocurrency exchange or over-the-counter, tokens can be traded for other cryptocurrencies or fiat money (in the case of utility tokens) after the ICO (OTC). ICOs and IPOs are similar in that they both involve a company issuing digital tokens or shares in order to obtain capital, which are then sold on the stock exchange (Ofir & Sadeh 2019). Because both ICOs and crowdfunding let companies and entrepreneurs use the Internet to raise money for their initiatives instead of using traditional financial channels, they can be compared (Lee & Parlour 2019).

Initial coin offerings (ICOs) have transformed the way start-ups raise capital. Since its inception in 2014, the ICO market has grown at a breakneck pace, with 1070 ICOs raising more than \$21 billion in 2018. (CoinSchedule 2018). Numerous studies have suggested various causes for the crypto market's quick rise, particularly initial coin offerings (ICOs). According to others, investors view cryptocurrencies as a "hedging strategy against unpredictable local currencies and geopolitical risk," Their growth is linked to a lingering distrust in the traditional banking sector following the 2008 financial crisis (Clements 2018). Additionally, heightened media attention (Clements, 2018) and exceptionally high returns for early investors (ROIs surpassing 50,000 percent) are contributing factors (Hacker Moon, 2017).

During the second half of 2018, the cryptocurrency market saw a significant slowdown: the total cryptocurrency market declined by over 85% from its high in months, while funding fell by over 90% between July 2018 and February 2019. It's (Dittmar & Wu 2019). Furthermore, the success rate of fundraising is decreasing. Empirical studies show that from the second half of 2017, the success rate of initial coin offers (ICOs) has declined dramatically. (Lee et al., 2018). Initial coin offers (ICOs) had an 81 percent success rate between 2014 and August 2017 according to Adhami et al. (2018). ICOs raised 90% of their funding goals in June 2017 but just 25% in November 2017, according to EY (2017). Between January 2017 and March 2018, just 48 percent of 2390 ICOs raised cash, according to Benedetti & Kostovetsky (2018); of them, only 26 percent were listed on crypto exchanges. Because of stricter regulations and a decrease in cryptocurrency prices, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, there has been a reduction in ICO activity, according to Lee et al (2018).

Numerous empirical studies have analyzed the geography of initial coin offerings and revealed a range of outcomes depending on the sample size and duration of the investigation. According to Amsden & Schweizer (2018), the United States is the world leader in terms of ICOs, followed by Russia, and the United States is also the world leader in terms of monies raised, with \$2.4 billion, followed by Switzerland's \$1.1 billion. According to Huang et al. (2020), the United States,

China, Russia, and Switzerland are the top countries for initial coin offerings, while the United States, Switzerland, Singapore, and Russia are the top countries for total funds raised.

With 53 ICO campaigns, Singapore was only surpassed by the global financial hub of the United States, which had 56 campaigns in terms of value. The British Virgin Islands and the Cayman Islands, on the other hand, hosted the ICO unicorns mentioned above but few other campaigns, putting Singapore in second place in terms of value. These numbers would indicate that Singapore is the most constant top performer in the number of initial coins offerings (ICOs) that it sponsors. According to many at the forefront of the emerging business, Singapore's ICO sector has a long way to go before it can be considered a world leader in its field.

On the other hand, Singapore's bullish cryptocurrency performance does not stop there. Singapore was indeed the third largest host of initial coin offerings (ICOs) in terms of funds raised (\$1.1 billion) and the second largest in terms of the total number of ICOs hosted (more than 2,000). As reported by Strategy&, a division of PwC that specializes in strategy consulting and collaboration with Crypto Valley, the United States, Singapore, and the United Kingdom continue to be the world leaders in terms of ICO volume. The trio completed a total of 157 successful initial coin offerings (ICOs) so far in 2018, with an additional 153 anticipated before the end of the year.

The burgeoning initial coin offering (ICO) market in Singapore is partially the result of limitations imposed elsewhere in Asia. Since China's well-publicized prohibition on initial coin offerings (ICOs) in September 2017, profitable start-ups seeking to raise capital have been funneled into the arms of the regional superpower's regional rivals. Mainland China has tightened its grip on blockchain start-ups, prompting them to flee to Hong Kong – which is also experiencing an increase in cryptocurrency and initial coin offering (ICO) activity – where there is more freedom than in Mainland China – and to Singapore, where they are launching their token sales. In the first half of 2018, Hong Kong saw the closure of 20 initial coin offerings (ICOs). A total of \$223 million was raised through those efforts, and the country will host a further 15 projects before the end of the year.

Factors Affecting Initial Coin Offering (ICO) Growth in Asian Countries

What do initial coin offerings (ICOs) bring to the table that other forms of entrepreneurial capital do not? That is why firms that utilize ICOs are thriving. This section addresses the reasons that have contributed to the expansion of initial coin offerings in Asian countries: (a) financing the development of decentralized networks; (b) Obtaining future customer commitment; (c) Creating irreversible governance terms; (d) Rapid liquidity provision; (e) accelerating the network effect; and (f) Cost savings associated with transactional and regulatory costs. This advantage provides background for our empirical examination of "success".

1. Financing development of decentralized networks

It's possible for the value of a blockchain network to be distributed among its token holders, rather than the network sponsors or intermediaries, as is the case with equity-funded start-ups like Facebook and Google. According to Popper (2016), content authors for open source systems, which have previously relied on volunteer labor, can now be compensated for their work (e.g., Wikipedia and Unix). It is possible to reward creators through an initial coin offering (ICO) without giving them any additional network authority than any other token holders (Canidio, 2018). A native token can also be used to reward platform helpers, such as validators, after the network is launched. A utility token is caught in the middle of a no-win situation. The ICO's capacity to kick-start network effects may be impeded if token holders place greater importance on preserving tokens than on using them. However, this does not mean that utility tokens should be held on to if the network's value does not rise in tandem with their own worth. Even though the technology is still growing, one way to alleviate this tension is by creating a token whose value is directly proportional to the amount of effort required to maintain the network. In this respect, Augur serves as a useful illustrative example. Decentralized prediction markets have been operating since 2016. Ether can be used for both wagering and payouts. This means that the natural outcome of every market may be determined by using REP (Augur's token). Assume the Patriots will win the Super Bowl in 2020 and that a market exists for predicting the outcome. If this is the case, what are the chances? It will be Augur's oracle approach that determines whether or not the Patriots win or lose the game. Anyone can stake REP and report on the outcome. If her report is accepted by the majority, the reporter will receive her REP back in addition to a portion of the reporting price. A fixed charge is charged to each share of REP to ensure that the company's market capitalization is at least five times greater than open market interest. Tokens are taken away if a reporter's account differs from that of the audience. Market growth means greater money for reporters willing to take a bigger risk with their right to report. These stakes hold a considerable amount of tokens at any given time, preventing the tokens from moving too quickly. For both the network and its clients, a token can be a valuable asset. In the appendix, we go into great detail about the Filecoin network. There is no expectation that customers will hold on to their tokens for an extended period of time. Tokens give service providers an incentive to participate in platform governance. Farmer-owned cooperatives, such as cooperatives owned by farmers, are similar to producer-owned cooperatives (Hansmann, 1996). Consequently, it should rise in value in tandem with the network's expansion and neither outpace or underpay it.

2. Obtaining future customer commitment

The second feature of ICOs is that they allow businesses to raise money from future customers, much like with crowd-fund-raising. For the first time in history, investors will not have a claim on the company's future cash flows and may be unrelated to its customers. Customers, like as venture capitalists, can help developers and users obtain access to network expansion gains. An early indication of demand for the brand's products is provided to the issuer (Demers & Lewellen 2003; Catalini & Gans 2018). ICOs have been advertised as a way to "democratize" access to new venture investment opportunities. 26 Investments from traditional institutional investors like hedge funds and venture capital firms are pouring into popular ICO tokens. Concerns have been raised that utility tokens may be owned by speculators rather than actual consumers because of this. According to Li and Mann (2018), purchasing tokens is a method for users to demonstrate their commitment to the network. Only by purchasing this token and committing to use it on the platform can a real commitment be made. The hypothesis further asserts that the existence of speculators does not limit the ability of utility tokens to solve coordination challenges; speculators would only purchase tokens if they felt the tokens would be held and utilized by platform users. Cong, Li, and Yi (2019) have developed an alternative theory of conjecture. Early adopters are attracted to token ownership because of the predicted price increase, which promotes adoption and network effects, according to the proponents of ICOs.

3. Creating irreversible governance terms

In addition, the immutable token generation contract serves as evidence of an issuer's commitment to token scarcity and governance, which lends credibility to the pledges made by the issuer. It will be possible for the platform to exist on its own after the token contract and platform have been implemented. Catalini & Gans (2018) take into account utility tokens, which serve as a means of exchange on a platform but have no governance or future cash flow rights. In terms of raising money, initial coin offers (ICOs) pose more questions than they answer. According to Canidio (2018), the capacity to issue tokens in the future (and hence obtain seigniorage money) causes commitment difficulties in the short term.

4. Rapid liquidity provision

Initial coin offerings (ICOs) provide early liquidity to startup investors because the tokens are freely transferable. You can buy and sell it for other digital currencies or cash on a cryptocurrency exchange. Liquidity of the token increases dramatically in this circumstance, as shown in the chart below. Tokens are a striking contrast to preferred equity used in venture capital and pre-sale contracts used in crowd-funding. Initial coin offers (ICOs) and initial public offerings (IPOs) share this advantage, rather (Zingales 1995). As of November 2018, only 47% of all ICO tokens had been listed on an exchange, therefore their liquidity is far from guaranteed. Liquidity may be restricted or nonexistent even for tokens that have been listed.

5. Accelerating the network effects

If you have tokens, you are obligated to contribute in some way to the platform's success, whether it is directly through tokens or indirectly via contributions. This helps to speed up the network effects (e.g., finding bugs or adding features). According to Cong et al. (2021), a rise in platform users is a result of predicted token price growth. This advantage underscores token value's dynamic character. Bakos & Halaburda (2018) model the sale of platform-specific utility tokens in an ICO as advantageous when preselling tokens can help to overcome the coordination problem among potential users, that is, to jump-start one-sided network effects. ICO models leverage token appreciation as a motivator for users to pre-join, which is a significant departure from the typical network effects that are at play. This is one of the most distinctive features. Because decentralized systems are frequently easily reproduced, it is critical that network effects be established as quickly as feasible in this setting. Holders of tokens may elect to hang onto them if they believe in the potential growth of their monetary value. On platform-based cryptocurrency exchanges, the procedures for creating tokens in the future or releasing current tokens from a reserve inventory are standard.

6. Cost savings associated with transactional and regulatory costs

Using a token instead of fiat money on the network reduces transaction costs, which is especially important when agents are spread across multiple nations. For example, the need for a standard unit of account or a need by an issuer to collect seigniorage could be met without employing a native token. Since Bitcoin and Ether have much lower transaction fees, a native currency isn't necessary. The platform may just as well use those cryptocurrencies instead. The transaction and regulatory costs associated with ICOs thus far have been essentially nonexistent, in stark contrast to initial public offerings (IPOs), which typically incur considerable underwriting and legal costs. For public companies, disclosure is required to be much more extensive than it is for private companies. ICO issuers increasingly regularly use token sale tactics that expressly state that the instrument is being issued as a security and that they are striving to comply with existing securities laws as regulatory scrutiny of the sector has intensified.

CONCLUSION

The growing number of articles and the current academic debate demonstrate the ICOs' developing reputation, credibility, and institutionalization as a new field of research in corporate finance. According to the findings of a systematic study and thematic analysis of publications, research on variables influencing ICO growth may be divided into six categories: (a) financing the development of decentralized networks; (b) obtaining future customer commitments; (c) establishing irreversible governance arrangements; (d) providing rapid liquidity; (e) accelerating the network effect; and (f) cost savings connected with transactional and regulatory costs. Our findings are the initial step toward furthering ICO research, providing as a scientific knowledge base to guide and drive future research initiatives. The examination of its drivers forecasts the post-campaign success of a probable future research proposal as a sort of crowdfunding in which tokens are speculated to acquire popularity as a viable alternative to finance. Because of the novel nature of this modality, we are aware that we currently face numerous hurdles. The issue stems from the relationship between the traditional market and ICOs. However, in order for this sort of crowdfunding to be successful in the long run, further research should look at the elements that influence ICO growth in Asian countries.

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